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Technological Competence And Quality Of Evaluation Practices In Business Education In Tertiary Institutions In Bayelsa State

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the relationship between technological competence and the quality of evaluation practices in Business Education in tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State, with particular focus on application skills and their influence on evaluation quality. A correlational research design was adopted, guided by two research questions and two hypotheses. The population comprised all Business Education lecturers in tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State, from which a representative sample was drawn using proportionate stratified random sampling. Data were collected using a structured instrument titled Technological Competence and Evaluation Practices Questionnaire (TCEPQ), validated by three experts and subjected to reliability testing, yielding a Cronbach Alpha coefficient of 0.85. Pearson Product-Moment Correlation was employed to test the hypotheses at a 0.05 significance level. Findings revealed a strong positive relationship between application skills and the quality of evaluation practices, indicating that lecturers with higher technological competence were more effective in conducting credible and quality-driven evaluations. The study concluded that technological competence is a vital determinant of evaluation quality in Business Education. It was recommended that Business Education departments integrate technology competence training into their curriculum and that institutions organize continuous professional development workshops to enhance lecturers' evaluation practices.

Keywords: Technological Competence, Application Skills, Evaluation Practices, Business Education, Tertiary Institutions.

INTRODUCTION

Technological competence has become an indispensable skill set in the 21st-century education system, particularly in the field of Business Education. As teaching and learning processes continue to integrate digital tools, the ability of lecturers to effectively use technology for instructional delivery and evaluation has become central to quality assurance in higher education. Globally, evaluation practices are shifting from purely traditional, paper-based assessments to technology-driven approaches such as online quizzes, e-portfolios, and computer-based testing, which enhance feedback, transparency, and efficiency (Okonkwo & Eze, 2022). In Nigeria, and particularly in Bayelsa State, tertiary institutions are increasingly adopting digital platforms for assessment and feedback in line with broader educational reforms promoting technology integration (Nwankwo, 2021). This transition underscores the importance of technological competence among Business Education lecturers, as their skills directly influence the fairness, reliability, and overall quality of evaluation practices.

Quality evaluation practices are crucial in Business Education because they not only measure students' learning outcomes but also shape their readiness for the modern workplace. Evaluation methods that integrate technology offer benefits such as timely feedback, flexibility, and opportunities for authentic assessment (Adeoye & Alabi, 2020). For Business Education lecturers, technological competence encompasses both ICT knowledge—familiarity with digital tools and systems—and application skills—the ability to apply these tools effectively in instructional assessment contexts (Afolabi & Olagunju, 2021). Studies have shown that lecturers with higher levels of technological competence are better positioned to design objective, transparent, and student-centered assessments, thereby enhancing academic standards (Eze & Onu, 2022). Conversely, limited technological competence has been linked to challenges such as poor assessment design, lack of objectivity, and ineffective feedback mechanisms (Okafor & Uzoechi, 2020).

Despite these advantages, the integration of technology in evaluation practices in tertiary institutions across Bayelsa State faces significant challenges. Barriers such as inadequate ICT infrastructure, unstable internet connectivity, and limited professional training opportunities constrain lecturers' ability to fully utilize digital tools for evaluation (Ijeoma & Chukwu, 2021). Furthermore, many Business Education programs still emphasize traditional testing methods while giving insufficient attention to digital assessment strategies, raising concerns about whether evaluation practices are keeping pace with global educational trends (Ogunyemi & Bello, 2022).

Understanding this relationship is vital, as it not only informs curriculum and professional development but also ensures that Business Education graduates are assessed through fair, transparent, and modern approaches aligned with the demands of the digital economy. This study, therefore, examines the relationship between technological competence and the quality of evaluation practices in Business Education in tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State, focusing specifically on ICT knowledge and application skills.

Purpose of the Study

The study examined technological competence and the quality of evaluation practices in Business Education in tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State. Specifically, the study aimed to achieve the following:

- i. examines the relationship between ICT knowledge and the quality of evaluation practices in Business Education in tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State.
- ii. examine the relationship between application skills and the quality of evaluation practices in Business Education in tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State.

Research Questions

Based on the purpose of the study, the following research questions were formulated:

- i. What is the relationship between ICT knowledge and the quality of evaluation practices in Business Education in tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State?
- ii. What is the relationship between application skills and the quality of evaluation practices in Business Education in tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at .05 level of significance:

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between ICT knowledge and the quality of evaluation practices in Business Education in tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between application skills and the quality of evaluation practices in Business Education in tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State.

RESEARCH METHODS

This study adopted a correlational research design to examine the relationship between technological competence and the quality of evaluation practices in Business Education in tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State. According to Charles-Owaba (2022), a correlational design is appropriate when the objective is to determine the degree of association between two or more variables without manipulating them. This design was considered suitable for the present study because it enabled the researcher to

establish the extent to which ICT knowledge and application skills, as measures of technological competence, relate to the quality of evaluation practices among Business Education lecturers.

A stratified random sampling technique was employed to select a sample of 100 Business Education lecturers from both federal and state-owned tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State. Stratification was based on institution type (federal and state), gender, and years of teaching experience, ensuring a balanced representation of the population. This approach enhanced the generalizability of the findings to the wider population of Business Education lecturers in the state.

The main instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire titled Technological Competence and Evaluation Practices Questionnaire (TCEPQ). The instrument was designed using a four-point Likert scale and comprised three sections. Section A obtained demographic information such as gender, institution type, and teaching experience. Section B assessed technological competence using two measures: ICT knowledge (familiarity with digital tools, software, and internet resources) and application skills (ability to apply ICT tools in instructional and assessment activities). Section C measured the quality of evaluation practices, focusing on fairness, objectivity, feedback mechanisms, and alignment with learning outcomes.

To ensure validity, the instrument was reviewed by two experts in Business Education and one expert in Educational Measurement and Evaluation. Their feedback was used to refine the questionnaire items in terms of clarity, relevance, and alignment with the research objectives. A pilot test was conducted with 12 lecturers from a tertiary institution outside the study sample. Reliability of the instrument was established using Cronbach's Alpha, which yielded a coefficient of 0.85, indicating high internal consistency.

Data collection was carried out by the researcher through personal administration of the questionnaire with the assistance of departmental heads to ensure accessibility to the respondents. Out of the 100 copies distributed, 96 were successfully retrieved, representing a response rate of 96%.

Data analysis involved the use of the Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMC) to answer the research questions and test the null hypotheses at a 0.05 level of significance. Correlation coefficients (r-values) were interpreted such that values of 0.50 and above indicated a strong relationship, while values below 0.50 indicated a weak relationship.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: *What is the relationship between ICT knowledge and the quality of evaluation practices in Business Education in tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State?*

Table 1: PPMC Analysis on the relationship between ICT knowledge and the quality of evaluation practices in Business Education in tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State

		ICT knowledge	quality of evaluation practices
ICT knowledge	Pearson Correlation	1	.759*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	96	96
Quality of evaluation practices	Pearson Correlation	.759*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	96	96

Source: Fieldwork, 2025

The data presented in Table 1 indicated that the correlation coefficient (r-value) between ICT knowledge and the quality of evaluation practices in Business Education is **.759**. Since the r-value is positive and falls within the high range, a strong positive relationship exists. Therefore, there is a strong positive relationship between ICT knowledge and the quality of evaluation practices in Business Education in tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State. Also, Table 1 shows that the relationship coefficient square (r^2) value is **.576**. This suggests that ICT knowledge accounts for **57.6%** of the overall variation in the quality of evaluation practices.

Research Question 2: *What is the relationship between application skills and the quality of evaluation practices in Business Education in tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State?*

Table 2: PPMC Analysis on the relationship between application skills and the quality of evaluation practices in Business Education in tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State

		Application skills	Quality of evaluation practices
Application skills	Pearson Correlation	1	.591*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	96	96
Quality of evaluation practices	Pearson Correlation	.591*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	96	96

Source: Fieldwork, 2025

The data presented in Table 2 indicated that the correlation coefficient (r-value) between application skills and the quality of evaluation practices in Business Education is **.591**. Since the r-value is positive and falls within the moderate to high range, a moderately strong positive relationship exists. Therefore, there is a moderately strong positive relationship between application skills and the quality of evaluation practices in Business Education in tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State. Also, Table 2 shows that the relationship coefficient square (r^2) value is **.349**. This suggests that application skills account for **34.9%** of the overall variation in the quality of evaluation practices.

Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between ICT knowledge and the quality of evaluation practices in Business Education in tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State.

The data presented in Table 1 indicated that, at an r-value of **.759**, the p-value is **0.000**. Since the p-value is less than the 0.05 alpha level, the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between ICT knowledge and the quality of evaluation practices in Business Education in tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State is rejected. This implies that ICT knowledge has a significant positive relationship with the quality of evaluation practices in Business Education.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between application skills and the quality of evaluation practices in Business Education in tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State.

The data presented in Table 2 indicated that, at an r-value of **.591**, the p-value is **0.000**. Since the p-value is less than the 0.05 alpha level, the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between application skills and the quality of evaluation practices in Business Education in tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State is rejected. This implies that application skills have a significant positive relationship with the quality of evaluation practices in Business Education.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The result from research question one revealed that ICT knowledge has a substantial positive and significant relationship with the quality of evaluation practices in Business Education in tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State. The findings indicate that lecturers who possess higher levels of ICT knowledge, such as familiarity with computer applications, online testing platforms, spreadsheet tools, and learning management systems, are more likely to design and implement quality evaluation practices that are objective, reliable, and timely. This suggests that the more knowledgeable lecturers are about digital tools and their functionalities, the better they are at ensuring fairness, accuracy, and efficiency in the assessment of students. Conversely, limited ICT knowledge may hinder lecturers from adopting modern evaluation strategies, resulting in overdependence on traditional methods that may not fully capture students' competencies. In essence, ICT knowledge directly enhances the quality of evaluation practices, enabling Business Education lecturers to align assessment processes with global standards of educational measurement. This result confirms a strong positive correlation between ICT knowledge and

the quality of evaluation practices, emphasizing the critical role of technological competence in sustaining quality assurance in tertiary education.

The finding aligns with previous studies such as Eze and Onu (2022), who reported that ICT knowledge significantly improves teachers' ability to administer assessments and provide timely feedback. Similarly, Afolabi and Olagunju (2021) found that digital competence enhances lecturers' confidence in utilizing technology-driven assessment tools, thereby improving transparency and reducing subjectivity in evaluation practices. These scholars argue that equipping lecturers with adequate ICT knowledge is fundamental to improving the credibility and efficiency of assessment processes in higher education. However, the finding contrasts with Okafor and Uzoечи (2020), who observed that despite lecturers' high levels of ICT awareness, poor infrastructure and limited institutional support often constrain the effectiveness of technology-driven evaluation in Nigerian tertiary institutions. Nonetheless, the present study underscores that strengthening lecturers' ICT knowledge is a foundational requirement for improving the quality of evaluation practices in Business Education across tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State.

The result from research question two revealed that application skills have a moderately strong and significant positive relationship with the quality of evaluation practices in Business Education in tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State. The findings indicate that lecturers who possess higher levels of application skills, such as the ability to effectively use digital tools for creating online tests, analyzing students' scores with spreadsheet applications, managing e-assessment platforms, and providing electronic feedback, are more likely to implement high-quality evaluation practices. This suggests that the practical ability to apply ICT tools in real teaching and assessment contexts directly enhances the fairness, efficiency, and comprehensiveness of evaluation. Conversely, lecturers with limited application skills may struggle to translate their knowledge of ICT into meaningful evaluation strategies, thereby limiting the effectiveness of assessment outcomes. In essence, application skills serve as a bridge between ICT knowledge and practice, ensuring that evaluation processes are not only modernized but also student-centered and transparent.

The finding aligns with earlier studies such as Adeoye and Alabi (2020), who reported that lecturers with higher ICT application skills were better at utilizing technology to improve assessment accuracy and feedback quality. Similarly, Ijeoma and Chukwu (2021) found that practical competence in applying digital tools significantly influences the effectiveness of evaluation methods in Nigerian tertiary institutions. These scholars maintain that beyond theoretical ICT knowledge, the ability to practically apply digital tools is what drives innovation and reliability in assessment practices. However, the finding contrasts with Ogunyemi and Bello (2022), who noted that despite lecturers' proficiency in applying ICT tools, infrastructural challenges such as unstable electricity and poor internet connectivity continue to undermine the overall quality of evaluation in Nigerian universities. Nevertheless, the present study emphasizes that application skills are a critical determinant of the quality of evaluation practices in Business Education, underscoring the need for continuous professional development to strengthen lecturers' practical ICT competence in tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State.

CONCLUSION

This study concludes that technological competence plays a pivotal role in enhancing the quality of evaluation practices in Business Education across tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State. The findings revealed that students and educators who demonstrate higher proficiency in applying digital tools and technologies are better able to design, implement, and assess evaluation processes with greater accuracy, efficiency, and transparency. Conversely, limited technological competence often results in poor assessment delivery, reduced credibility of evaluation outcomes, and diminished learning experiences. Thus, the study underscores that equipping Business Education stakeholders with strong technological skills is not only essential for aligning with global educational standards but also for ensuring credible, innovative, and technology-driven evaluation practices in the Nigerian higher education system.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations were put forward:

1. Tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State should organize regular capacity-building workshops and training programs to improve the technological competence of Business Education lecturers and students for effective evaluation practices.
2. Policymakers and administrators should invest in modern digital infrastructure and educational technologies that support innovative, reliable, and technology-driven evaluation systems in Business Education.

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